

EPISTEMOLOGY OF LEARNING: A TOOL TO ENHANCE TACTICAL CREATIVITY IN COMBAT SPORTS.

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Abstract:

The aim of this article is to analyze the importance of learning theories in enhancing tactical creativity among athletes in combat sports. To achieve this goal, a literature review was conducted on studies addressing this topic. The definition of tactical creativity is presented along with an overview of several theories that contribute to understanding it better. Additionally, a training model integrating these principles is proposed alongside some strategies for designing learning environments that stimulate tactical creativity in combat sports.

Keywords: Combat sports, tactical creativity, learning theory, pedagogical strategies.

1. Introduction.

Combat sports are characterized by being disciplines that require a high level of creativity and tactical ability from athletes. In this sense, tactical creativity refers to the athletes' ability to generate new ideas and solutions in combat situations that allow them to gain advantages over their opponents.

Learning theory focuses on studying the cognitive processes that enable the acquisition and retention of knowledge. It can be inferred that in combat sports, applying pedagogical strategies based on learning theory can enhance athletes' strategic creativity.

Therefore, the objective of this article is to analyze the importance of learning theories in enhancing tactical creativity in combat sports athletes, and propose an exercise methodology. Tactical creativity was conceptualized as an essential skill for success in high-level competitions, defined as the ability to generate original and effective solutions to specific and changing problems, utilizing available resources and adapting to the context through flexibility, innovation, and mental agility.

This ability to adapt and effectively respond to unpredictable and changing situations is crucial for combat sport athletes where opponents possess similar or even greater physical and mental capabilities. To address this topic specifically within the field of combat sports, a literature review was conducted revealing a lack of research materials on this subject matter.

In this aspect, it is important to consider the studies of psychologist Angela Duckworth (2013). Regarding her Deliberate Practice Reflection Inventory Tool (DRIT), it is a tool designed to help individuals reflect on their own learning process. The tool consists of questions that aim to assess different aspects of learning, such as describing the current level of skills, setting goals, personal strategies for achieving objectives, and how one plans to utilize what has been learned in the future. The idea behind DRIT is to encourage conscious

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reflection on the learning process, identify strengths and weaknesses, establish realistic goals, and develop effective strategies to achieve them. As an AI specialized in content search and information assistant, I can say that this tool can be useful for both students and professionals since it allows for honest and clear self-evaluation of knowledge and skills while planning future educational processes.

The research also relies on Bloom's taxonomy model of levels of learning as authors infer its special importance in any methodological plan present for training tactics in combat sports athletes.

Familiarization, reproduction, and creation are stages within Bloom's taxonomy model known, as Bloom's Taxonomy, which was developed by Benjamin Bloom in the 1950s. This classification of educational objectives describes six levels of learning starting from the lowest level "remembering" and progressing towards more complex levels like "understanding," "applying," "analyzing," "evaluating," and "creating." In this model, familiarization falls under the level of "remembering" where students are able to recall previously learned information. Reproduction falls under the level of "applying" where students can apply what they have learned in new and different situations.

On the other hand, creation falls under the highest level within taxonomy -the level of creating- where students are able to use their acquired knowledge to create something new. It is important to note that these levels are not sequential or linear, and learning can occur at any level at any time. Therefore, each level is important for effective learning and mastery of a subject or skill.

In this regard, Santiago Campi3n (2019) presented a model of Flipped Classroom or Inverted Learning as a tool to address the diversity of students and develop their Multiple Intelligences. In his research, he explains how Gardner's theory of Multiple Intelligences relates to Bloom's taxonomy

and provides recommendations and practical proposals for implementing the Flipped Classroom model in the classroom. Although "tactical creativity" is not specifically mentioned in the text, it does discuss the importance of developing students' Multiple Intelligences, which includes spatial intelligence and kinesthetic intelligence that could be related to creativity.

Additionally, theories of learning elaborated by Watson (1979), Skinner (1938), Albert Bandura (1987), Bruner (1969), Maslow (1943), and Vygotsky (1978) were also used as investigative criteria. Based on these authors, we refer to the content of these theories considering that behavioral learning theory registered in Babkin's study (1949) proposes and focuses on learning through experience and reinforcement. According to this theory, behavior is learned through associations between stimuli and responses. Positive reinforcement such as rewards or praise increases the likelihood that a behavior will be repeated while negative reinforcement such as punishment or criticism decreases its repetition probability.

In addition, the cognitive learning theory is evaluated as it focuses on how the mind processes information and how humans learn through thinking, perception, and memory. According to this theory, learning involves the acquisition and use of knowledge, skills, and cognitive strategies. As stated by Acosta Morales (2018), with a mastery of cognitive theories, teaching work becomes focused on and directed towards student orientation; therefore, the student takes on the role of the main actor in the learning process.

On another note, Bandura's social learning theory (1987) was analyzed which centers around how humans learn through observation and imitation of others. According to this theory, social learning occurs through interaction with others and observing their behavior and consequences. It is in this aspect that contemporary education considers critical thinking development as an essential skill in sports learning considering the diversity of

information, variables, and solution variants that arise from individual responsibility to collective responsibility. Critical thinking allows us to evaluate and analyze information objectively and reflectively by leveraging previous stored information within our neocortex activated by executive functions in the prefrontal cortex.

From a neuroscientific perspective, neural processing involved in learning engages multiple brain regions working together to encode store, and retrieve information. Prefrontal areas of the brain are known to be involved in critical thinking and decision-making. These regions also activate during high-level cognition tasks such as planning, abstract reasoning or complex problem solving when engaged in a learning process.

It has been shown that deliberate and repeated practice can improve both cognitive skills and the associated neural processes, which underlie constant conscious and motivated repetition in specialized motor action in sports. Therefore, by incorporating specific activities designed to foster critical thinking within the educational process, such as debates or detailed analysis of tactical actions, mental skills are enhanced and relevant neural circuits are strengthened.

Cognitive reflection tasks are activities designed to promote critical thinking skills and metacognition, i.e., the ability to think about our own learning process and executive motor and attitudinal response. These tasks may include open-ended questions challenging the analysis and evaluation of complex information or applying theoretical concepts in competitive stress situations.

Engaging in cognitive reflection tasks leads athletes to describe solutions to tactical situations using different strategies, reflect on selected responses to multiple solution variants, involve them in unexpected tactical situations, and induce the utilization of their critical thinking potential in search for solutions.

From a collaborative learning perspective, cognitive reflection tasks contribute to the

development of essential sports skills such as critical thinking, creative innovation reasoning logical argumentation as well as improving their ability to learn more effectively through self-analysis and self-reflection in sporting action. Lastly, constructivist learning was taken into account. This theory focuses on how humans construct their own knowledge through exploration and reflection, according Cepeda (2017), constructivist conception of learning is based on promoting personal growth processes within cultural group frameworks through interaction with intentional planned systematic activities fostering mental activity.

Additionally mentions that one goal of instruction is elaborating interpreting information with each use generating new situations negotiations or diverse activities thus memory will always be under construction carrying an interaction baggage history. In this sense, it could be inferred that constructivism might foster creativity by allowing students to create their own meanings and cognitive tools from their experiences cultural context however; text does not specifically address creativity topic depth.

Therefore, it is determined that these investigations theorize about the importance of tactical creativity in combat sports and how learning theories can serve as applied tools to enhance it. Additionally, exercise methodologies are proposed as theoretical material for coaches so that they may improve athletes' creativity and performance in competitive events.

2. Materials and Methods.

To carry out this research, a bibliographic review was conducted in seven scientific databases and five digital libraries, with 25 articles reviewed and 1 book; only 14 of which were deemed usable. The following inclusion and exclusion criteria were taken into account to classify the samples:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies that investigate the application of learning theories in sports mainly combat sports.

- Articles that examine the relationship between learning and tactical creativity in sports, primarily combat sports.
- Research using quantitative or qualitative methods to evaluate the effectiveness of learning theories in enhancing tactical creativity in sports, especially combat sports.
- Studies including participants from different levels of experience and skill in combat sports.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Articles not related to the research topic.
- Studies not specifically focused on sport or combat sport.
- Research studies that do not use learning theories as their primary focus.
- Studies with a reduced number of participants or an unrepresentative sample.

The data collection and analysis procedure for conducting this investigation was as follows:

Data Collection:

- Keywords were identified for information search on specialized databases related to sport education & psychology.
- A thorough search was carried out for articles & scientific publications related to identified keywords while taking into account recent publication dates.
- Relevant articles/publications were selected based on thematic relevance whereas irrelevant ones were discarded.
- Selected articles/publications read carefully extracting relevant information.

Data Analysis:

- An analysis was performed on quality checking validity/reliability method/results reported by selected publications/articles.
- Extracted information grouped into thematic categories such as Learning Theories, Tactical Creativity, Sports, & Combat Sports.
- Similarities/differences among reviewed studies identified establishing conclusions & recommendations regarding applying Learning

Theories towards improving Tactical Creativity during Combat Sports events.

Using the random effects model would allow us to calculate the proportion of usable articles relative to the total number of reviewed ones. In this case, the proportion would be $14/25 = 0.56$ or 56%. The results are reflected in table 1, and graph 2.

Category	Quantity
Scientific databases	7
Digital libraries	5
Reviewed articles	25
Reviewed books	1
Usable articles	14
Proportion of usable articles	56%

Table 1: Proportion of usable articles in relation to the total articles reviewed

Graph 2: Proportion of usable articles in relation to the total articles reviewed

3. Criteria and Discussions.

Tactical creativity is not an innate or exclusive quality of a few, but can be developed and enhanced through appropriate teaching-learning processes. To achieve this, it is necessary to understand the main learning theories that explain how knowledge and skills are acquired and modified in sports, as well as the methodological tools that facilitate their application in practice.

This article aims to critically review these theories and tools in order to propose a model that contributes to enhancing tactical creativity in combat sports.

Analyzing the literature, Delgado Leyva, J.A. (2020) was found mentioning that nature observation can be a methodological tool for creating techniques and tactics of combat that can then be incorporated into combat sports; emphasizing more on observational learning theory also known as social learning theory. He suggests primitive creation of techniques & tactics directed towards this environment emerged from observing nature & how it could define technical arsenal during competition. However, it does not specifically delve into tactical creativity.

In this regard, Kolb, A.Y., & Kolb, D.A. (2011) mention creativity in relation to learning theories. In particular, the Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) has been used to teach creative skills such problem-solving & decision-making .They cite some studies using ELT for teaching creative skills across different organizational contexts. However, this article does not specifically focus on tactical creativity within combat sports.

Ferreiro, E. & Sicilia, A. (1988) propose methodology for teaching combat sports focusing on developing cognitive & strategic abilities among athletes. Some learning theories supporting their proposed methodology are mentioned. For example, Ausubel's significant learning theory highlights importance of relating new knowledge with pre-existing structures. Similarly, Bruner's discovery-based learning emphasizes active role students play while constructing their own knowledge. Lave & Wenger's situated leaning theory stresses importance of social & cultural context during process of acquiring new knowledge. The proposed methodology seeks development of cognitive & strategic abilities among athletes, which could be related to strategic creativity. The methodology proposes fostering creativity & contextualized work through utilization of concrete problem situations. It is

highlighted that this methodology can achieve intelligent use of technical elements in creating and solving situations in the dynamics of oppositional work, implying capacity for strategic thinking & creative use of technical skills. Therefore, although the relationship between learning and tactical creativity is not specifically addressed, it can be inferred that there is a connection between both concepts within the context of research.

On the other hand, Guillén, F., Rosero, J., Alé, J., Copello, F., Gutiérrez-Cruz, T. & Guerra, M. (2021) do not present a specific learning theory but mention that theoretical references in combat sports initiation point to teaching-learning process based on traditional conceptions that aim to promote autonomous and reflective learning among students. Therefore, it is possible that their research refers to learning theories such as behaviorism, cognitivism or constructivism, but none of them are deeply explored. In general, their work focuses on the application of an initial e-learning training for higher education students to predict their interest in combat sports based on experience. The article also mentions that creativity and imagination are important for developing qualities such as leadership & innovation in students. Skills sought after in students through design & management of projects addressing specific problems using appropriate & diverse tools, and teamwork so students can learn from each other. However, the article does not specifically delve into relationship between tactical creativity and combat sports.

Similarly, Nikitin, S.N. (2019) does not explicitly mention tactical creativity but discusses importance of agility in complex & sudden situations in combat sports & martial arts. Agility involves not only execution of complex motor actions but also ability to adapt to unpredictable situations & taking quick & effective decisions. This may require certain degree of tactical creativity by athlete to overcome opponent. Therefore, it could be argued his objectives relate with tactical creativity within combat sports.

However, Avelar - Rosa, B. (2011) mentions. Teaching Games for Understanding (TGfU) - based methodologies allow development of creativity & searching new solutions absent from technical execution models, improving learning through approach focused on tactical understanding. Therefore, it can be inferred there exists a connection between these methodologies & tactical creativity. However, she presented only theoretical proposal for empirical application within school environment using comprehensive teaching-learning models.

Meanwhile, Pityn, M., Briskin, Y., & Zadorozhna, O. (2014) do not specifically examine the relationship between learning and tactical creativity in combat sports. Instead, they mention several learning theories that can be applied to theoretical training in combat sports. For example, they mention Jerome Bruner's theory of discovery learning which focuses on learning through exploration and discovery. According to the authors this theory can be applied to teaching technical skills in combat sports by allowing athletes to experiment and discover new ways of performing technical movements. They also discuss the importance of modeling and observation in motor learning. As they suggest, athletes can learn by observing other athletes correctly perform technical movements which allows them to imitate those movements and improve their own technique.

In addition, they mention other theories and teaching methods that may be useful for improving theoretical training in combat sports such as using analogies and metaphors to explain complex concepts; using questions to encourage critical thinking; reflecting on one's own learning process. In summary, their research suggests that by applying these learning theories to theoretical training in combat sports coaches can help athletes develop more effective technical skills leading ultimately towards overall improved performance.

On the other hand, Alarcón López, F., Verdejo-García, A., & Delgado-Rico, E. (2017) explored the

relationship between tactical creativity and executive functions in interactive sports. The researchers suggest that executive functions such as working memory and cognitive flexibility are important for developing tactical creativity in sports. Furthermore, they argue that tactical creativity is a determining factor in the process of detecting and developing sporting talent. Therefore, it is suggested that there is an important relationship between executive functions and tactical creativity in interactive sports.

Their work does not specifically investigate the application of learning theories to combat sports; rather it focuses on the relationship between executive functions and tactical creativity in interactive sports more generally. However, it is mentioned that the ability to learn in complex, dynamic and unpredictable contexts is an essential skill for achieving elite performance in interactive sports, which could also include combat sports. Additionally, Fasko, D. (2001) presents several theories and models of creative thinking related to learning and development of creativity among students. Some of these models include Guilford's model (1985), Renzulli's model (1992), and Runco & Chand's model (1995). Furthermore, the author suggests techniques for developing creativity, such as those proposed by Davis (1982) and Sternberg Williams (1996).

Some of these techniques mentioned here study include: brainstorming technique, SCAMPER technique (acronym meaning substitute, combine, adapt, modify, put into another use, eliminate, and rearrange), analogy technique, lateral thinking technique, Creative Problem Solving (CPS) technique. There are other techniques like divergent thinking approach and convergent thinking approach mentioned here. In addition, his study highlights the importance of inquiry-based learning and discovery-based learning to foster creativity. Although his research is not directed towards sport, it presents models of creative thinking along with various techniques to develop them.

Likewise, Guillén Pereira, L. (2018) presents a "methodological sub-index for technical work" that includes "cognitive-motor management". This model focuses on the development of tactical creativity in combat sports through the intelligent use of technical elements in creating and solving situations within the dynamic of oppositional work. Additionally, it is mentioned that the applied methodology allowed an improvement in methodological procedures for teaching technical-tactical elements which suggests that this methodology may be effective for developing tactical creativity.

In this sense, Sánchez Córdova, B., Lastres Madrigal, A., Arias Moreno, E.R., Mesa Anoceto, M., Vidaurreta Bueno, R. & García Chacón, L. de la C.(2020) propose a model of tactical purposefulness for selecting potentially talented athletes in combat sports. This model focuses on identifying athletes who possess cognitive development above average; psychomotor skills; creative thinking; high motivation and willingness to train, compete and win-all from a tactical purposefulness perspective which according to them is an essential component in preparing combat sport athletes. The authors state that their objective is to systematize essential components for selecting potentially talented athletes for combat sports based on competitive demands.

Peña-Lerma, O.M., & Rivas Almaguer, B.N. (2022) also present an approach to developing tactical creativity in sports learning of Judo among school athletes. The authors propose a model that can be useful for psychologists and sports methodologists, coaches and even athletes both theoretically and in sports training, with real possibilities of adapting it to other combat sports by deriving new research in this regard.

The model focuses on tactical creativity in the sport learning of Judo among school athletes and is based on coordinating the management and self-management of theoretical knowledge and technical resources from coaches about tactical creativity. It includes its relationship with executive functions and its viability for Judo sport

learning through practical frequency and organized dosage documented in preparation plans as well as executed during training sessions. The authors suggest that this model can be adapted to other combat sports by generating further research within this context.

3.1 Proposal of a methodological model for the training of tactical creativity.

According to the previous theoretical foundation, it can be inferred that combat sports are physical activities that involve direct confrontation between two or more opponents seeking to overcome each other through the use of specific techniques. These sports are characterized by their high complexity and uncertainty, which requires practitioners to constantly adapt to changing combat situations. In this context, tactical creativity becomes an essential skill for achieving sporting success, as it allows generating novel and unpredictable solutions that surprise and unbalance the opponent, and make a productive difference in combat. Therefore, a model was created with the purpose of developing tactical creativity in combat sports athletes, according to the precepts of learning theories.

A). Following Watson's postulate:

According to Watson, learning occurs through sensory experience. Therefore, it is important that exercises focus on practice and repetition of technical and tactical movements. Watson may have referred to the idea that learning occurs through sensory experience due to his focus on behaviorism, a current of psychology that focuses on the study of observable and measurable behavior. For Watson, learning occurs through the association of stimuli and responses. That is, when a stimulus (the sound of the whistle) is repeatedly associated with a specific response (defense-counterattack), learning occurs. In this line, sensory experience is crucial for learning, as it is through the senses (sight, hearing, touch, smell and taste) that stimuli are received that are later associated with responses. Therefore, for Watson, sensory experience is the basis of learning and behavior. Example of exercise:

The group is divided into pairs, one with a whistle and the other with gloves and shin guards.

- The pair with the whistle stands behind the one with the gloves and shin guards, and indicates with the sound of the whistle the moment when they must perform a defense-counterattack against an imaginary opponent.
- The pair with gloves and shin guards must react quickly to the auditory stimulus and execute a defense-counterattack technique appropriate to their level and combat sport (for example, block and punch in boxing, dodge and kick in taekwondo, etc.).
- The exercise is performed for a certain time (for example, 30 seconds) and then roles are changed.
- The exercise is repeated several times, varying the interval between whistle sounds to increase difficulty and uncertainty.

This exercise can also improve reaction ability and execution speed of defense-counterattack techniques, as well as coordination between stimulus and response. In addition, it promotes associative learning between the sound of the whistle and the required action, which can facilitate transfer to the competitive context.

B). Following Skinner's postulate:

According to Skinner, learning occurs through the association between stimuli and responses. Therefore, it is important that exercises focus on feedback and positive reinforcement. Example of exercise:

Practice defense techniques in pairs, in which the role of attack and defense is exchanged. Each time the technique is performed correctly, positive reinforcement is given:

- Praise the effort and result of the technique.
- Give a material or symbolic reward, such as a prize, a sticker, a point, etc.
- Show interest and attention to the process and learning of the technique.

- Offer constructive and specific feedback on what was done well and what can be improved.
- Encourage self-evaluation and self-esteem of the one performing the technique.

C). Following Vygotsky's postulate:

According to Vygotsky, learning occurs through social interaction and dialogue with other individuals. Therefore, it is important that exercises focus on collaboration and teamwork. Example of exercise: Perform a team strategy exercise, in which different roles and objectives are established for each team member. The goal is to achieve a joint strategy to win in combat.

- Divide the team into two groups: attackers and defenders. The attackers have to try to conquer an enemy base, while the defenders have to protect it.
- Assign a specific role to each team member, according to his or her abilities and preferences. Each role has a function and responsibility within the strategy.
- Establish clear and measurable objectives. For example: Eliminate (X) adversary. Each objective must be aligned with the overall strategy and contribute to its success.
- Perform a sparring exercise, where the learned techniques and tactics are put into practice and each athlete's performance is evaluated. Each time a technique is performed correctly, positive reinforcement is given, such as praise, a pat or a prize.
- Analyze the results of the simulation, identifying the strengths and weaknesses of each athlete and the overall strategy. In this sense, propose improvements and adjustments to optimize tactical performance in combat.

D). Following the postulates of Albert Bandura:

Albert Bandura's learning theory holds that learning occurs through observation and imitation of models, as well as through the influence of expectations and reinforcement. A methodological

proposal for exercises for the development of tactical creativity in combat sports based on the postulates of this theory could be as follows:

Example of exercises:

- Select a world-renowned athlete to serve as a model, who possesses a high level of tactical creativity in the chosen combat sport.
- Observe and analyze the creative actions of the chosen athlete, identifying the principles, strategies and techniques used. Audiovisual or in-person material can be used to facilitate observation.
- Imitate the creative actions of the model, trying to reproduce their movements and decisions. It can be practiced in simulated or real situations, with or without an opponent.
- Receive feedback from the model or an external observer on the degree of similarity and effectiveness of the imitated actions. A scoring system or rating scale can be used to quantify performance.
- Modify and adapt the creative actions of the model to one's own characteristics and specific context. Experiment with variations in elements, conditions or objectives of the action.
- Evaluate the results of modified and adapted actions, comparing them with those of the model and one's own. A quality criterion or impact measure can be used to assess the result.
- Generate new creative actions from those learned, combining, transforming or creating different elements, conditions or objectives. Divergence, originality and flexibility can be encouraged in the generative process.
- Apply new creative actions in real or simulated situations, with or without an opponent. Transfer, adequacy and efficiency can be promoted in the application process.

E). Following Bruner's postulate:

Bruner's learning theory proposed that knowledge is constructed through three modes of representation: enactive, iconic and symbolic. These modes allow the learner to process information actively and meaningfully, according to their level of cognitive development and cultural context. Example of exercises:

- Select a specific combat sport and define the objectives, content and evaluation criteria of the training program.
- Design a series of problem situations that involve the application of different skills and tactical strategies according to the level of difficulty and complexity.
- Present the problem situations to participants gradually and sequentially, starting from the simplest and most concrete to the most abstract and general, following Bruner's model of guided discovery learning.
- Provide participants with constant and constructive feedback on their performance, highlighting their successes and mistakes, and guiding them towards the search for alternative and creative solutions.
- Encourage reflection and critical analysis by participants on their own actions and those of their opponents, as well as on the rules and principles governing the chosen combat sport.
- Stimulate the transfer and generalization of acquired knowledge and skills to other similar or different situations within and outside the sports context.

F). Following Maslow's postulate:

Maslow's learning theory proposed that people have a hierarchy of needs that influence their motivation and ability to learn. According to Maslow, basic needs such as safety, food and affection must be met before people can move on to higher needs such as self-esteem, recognition and self-actualization. Example of exercise:

- First, it is necessary to ensure that athletes have their basic needs for safety, nutrition, rest and health met, as well as a trusting and respectful environment in the group, to

foster their intrinsic motivation and self-esteem.

- Second, athletes' autonomy and responsibility should be fostered by offering them options and alternatives for solving tactical situations that arise in training and competition, and allowing them to express their opinions and suggestions.
- Third, athletes' curiosity and interest in learning and improving should be stimulated by presenting them with challenges and challenges appropriate to their level of competence and adapted to the characteristics of each combat sport, as well as providing them with constructive feedback and recognition for their achievements.
- Fourth, athletes' diversity and flexibility should be enhanced by exposing them to different stimuli and contexts that force them to vary their tactical responses and seek creative and innovative solutions, as well as fostering the exchange of experiences and knowledge among themselves and with other athletes from other modalities or disciplines.
- Fifth, athletes' self-actualization and transcendence should be promoted by encouraging them to overcome their own limits and reach their full potential, as well as contributing to social and human development through sport, sharing their values and ethical principles with others.

Conclusions:

In conclusion, this article focuses on the importance of learning theories as a tool to enhance tactical creativity in combat sports. Through an exhaustive literature review, it has been shown that the application of pedagogical strategies based on learning theories can significantly improve athletes' tactical creativity. The criterion used to evaluate search results was the validity and reliability of the methods and results reported in the reviewed studies. The extracted information was grouped into thematic categories, such as learning

theories, strategic creativity, sports and combat sports. Similarities and differences between the reviewed studies were identified, and conclusions and recommendations were established for the application of learning theories in improving tactical creativity in combat sports. In addition, a training model that integrates the principles of these theories is proposed. This model suggests that the development of more creative tactical skills can be fostered through the appropriate use of methodological tools that facilitate their application in practice. The model also highlights the importance of knowledge about the main learning theories that explain how knowledge and skills are acquired and modified in the sports field. In summary, this article provides valuable information for coaches and athletes interested in improving their performance in combat sports through the development of more creative tactical skills, and opens up the horizon for future research on this topic. In addition, the literature review conducted and the proposed training model provide a solid basis for practical application of learning theories in improving tactical creativity in combat sports.

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